

Fascist Italy as the Heir of the Imperium Romanum

Celebration of Romanism as an ideological instrument of legitimation

Introduction

On May 9, 1936, at 9:45 p.m., on the balcony of Palazzo Venezia, Benito Mussolini proclaimed: “Italy, at last, has an empire of its own¹“ For Mussolini, revealing Italy as an “empire” was not just the simple use of a term. Still, it was to be the cornerstone of the large-scale adaptation of the Imperium Romanum that Fascism had made its primary goal. With this proclamation, a new era dawned for Italy, which is why the year in question was also meaningfully touted by Mussolini at the time as “anno zero”.

However, Italy's basic idea of using the Roman Empire as a political model existed before the Fascist era. Even during Italy's nation-building in 1861, ancient Rome was considered an important role model. This can be seen, among other things, in a statement by Camillo Cavour, which read: “Just as ancient Rome was once the capital of the world, so the new Rome should once again occupy this place”². The protagonists of the Kingdom of Italy, however, in the sense of a historical-political euphoria, were almost exclusively content with the idea of the ancient Mediterranean.

When fascism entered the Kingdom of Italy in 1922, Benito Mussolini declared Rome as the starting point, final goal, and myth of fascism³, seeing a lack of integration ideology. Fascist Italy, under this slogan, committed itself subsequently to acting as the historical heir of ancient Rome, establishing the restoration of the Imperium Romanum as the affirmative goal of fascism. The claim was made not only to use ancient Rome for political purposes in the form of a historical projection but also to elevate it to the spirit of the entire current and the Italian nation.

The first elements of a turn to Roman antiquity can already be seen in the initial phase of the fascist rise to power. This was the case, for example, with the formation of the “Camicia Nera” based on elite Roman troops. While Fascism succeeded in consolidating its position of power in Italy, under Mussolini, Romanism was staged in numerous areas, which convinced the Italian people to approve of an imperial expansionist policy. Italy's entry into the Second World War will be the temporal endpoint of our investigation.

¹ Benito Mussolini: *Scritti E Discorsi dell'Impero*. (Novembre 1935-XIV – 4 Novembre 1936-XV E.F.), Milano 1939, S. 115-120.

² Vgl. Camillo Benso conte di Cavour: *Opera parlamentaria del conte di Cavour*, o.O 1862., S. 361-362

³ Vgl. Richard Faber: *Das ewige Rom, oder, Die Stadt und der Erdkreis. Zur Archäologie "abendländischer" Globalisierung*, Würzburg 2000, S. 173.

The present work focuses on the central question of the means used to legitimize Fascist Italy as the rightful heir to the Imperium Romanum.

As an introduction to this topic, we first illuminate the extent to which ancient Rome already served as a model at the time of the Risorgimento. Then we will look at the tense situation after the end of the First World War, which the angry population generally called “Vittoria mutilata”. Then we will talk about the causes of the emergence of an increasing imperialist urge, which paved the way for the ambitions of fascism in Italy.

In the following, the identification with the symbol of the fasces is considered, which was consistently used under the influence of Benito Mussolini, both in party names and as a recurring emblem on flags. In particular, it examines how it was possible to give the Roman lictor bundle a genuine emblem character. Subsequently, by looking at three areas in which a deliberate orchestration of fascist Romanism took place, the so-called “romanità fascista” We will begin with the military organization of the March on Rome, with which fascism succeeded in gaining political domination in Italy. Mussolini's self-portrayal follows this in his heyday as the second Augustus and the representative large-scale building project of fascism, the Via dell Impero, in the heart of Rome.

In conclusion, a summary will be drawn about how the idea of a reconstruction of the Imperium Romanus could ideologically manifest itself in fascist Italy and in which period it was significant for the national mentality. The conclusion critically examines Italy's claim to embody an empire and Mussolini's self-image as the second August.

The Mission Statement of Rome in the Risorgimento

The march on Rome was supposed to usher in a new era for the Kingdom of Italy, which Benito Mussolini, appointed prime minister on October 30, 1922, placed under the guiding principle of a revival of the Roman Empire⁴. But even before the rise of fascism, Giuseppe Garibaldi, in 1870, set his goals for Italy under the auspicious oath: “Rome or death”⁵. Garibaldi's Italian unification movement, from 1815 to 1870, was not without reason known as the Risorgimento because “Risorgimento” means “revival” or “rebirth” in German. According to Garibaldi, ancient Rome was to rise again, in this sense, and fragmented Italy was to be reunited⁶.

⁴ Vgl. Heinz Malangré: *Blicke auf Europa.: Seine Wurzeln, sein Stamm, seine Äste, seine Krone*, Hamburg 2012, S. 463.

⁵ Vgl. Gustav Seibt: *Rom oder Tod: Der Kampf um die italienische Hauptstadt*, München 2011, S. 86.

⁶ Vgl. Federico Chabod: *storia della politica estera italiana*, Laterza 1951, S. 299.

The Italian revolutionary, Francesco Crispi, saw the reunification of Italy as the end of 1400 years of oppression and contempt for the Italian people. According to Crispi, the unification of Italy was accompanied by a glorious new beginning for Rome, which he described as follows: “at the origin Rome, always Rome, always the Roman cement”⁷. Crispi's statement represents Rome as the origin and the timeless cement that holds Italy together and unites it as a nation. From comments like these, it can be seen that the basic idea of linking up with the greatness of ancient Rome was undoubtedly present in the Kingdom of Italy even before Fascism.

However, after the Kingdom of Italy's unification, Rome's recovery quickly became secondary, and the idea of being the historical heir of Rome was only superficially considered. This circumstance soon led to the fact that in the population, increasingly, a loss of the integration ideology was perceived, as far as the guiding image of Rome was concerned. The crushing defeat at Adua in 1896 completely buried Italy's ambitions for colonial expansion. After this defeat, restoring the Imperium Romanum was out of the question, and Italy was content with the idea of a kingdom of its own⁸. The loss above put the Italian nation in a state of shock, and efforts to colonize other countries were halted. In the years that followed, the consolidation of colonies that had already been taken was given top priority, which is why historian Wolfgang Fengler describes the period from 1871 to 1907 as a phase in which Italian power in Africa was established⁹.

“Vittoria mutilata” after the first world war

After the colonies consolidated from 1871 to 1907, Italy tried to annex new countries. In the Italian-Turkish War, which lasted from 1911 to 1912, Italy prevailed over the Ottoman Empire and conquered Libya as a new colony. Aram Mattioli describes the course of this conflict as “a forgotten key event of the world war epoch”¹⁰. The victory in the Italo-Turkish War also increased Italy's motivation to assert itself on the European battlefield. Thus, in 1915, a year after the outbreak of World War I, Italy entered the war alongside the Allies.

Italy was considered one of the victorious nations at the war's end, but the population was unhappy and dubbed the victory “Vittoria mutilata” or “crippled victory.” This was felt

⁷ Vgl. Francesco Crispi: Discorsi parlamentari di Francesco Crispi pubblicati per deliberazione della Camera dei deputati, o.O. 1915, S. 311.

⁸ Vgl. Richard Bosworth: Italy the Least of the Great Powers, Italian Foreign Policy Before the First World War, Cambridge 2005, S. 2-13.

⁹ Vgl. Wolfgang Fengler: Politische Reformhemmnisse und ökonomische Blockierung in Afrika. Die Zentralafrikanische Republik und Eritrea im Vergleich, Baden-Baden 2001, S. 160.

¹⁰ Aram Mattioli: Ein vergessenes Schlüsselereignis der Weltkriegsepoche in: Asfa-Wossen Asserate u. Aram Mattioli (Hg.), Der Erste Faschistische Vernichtungskrieg. Die italienische Aggression gegen Äthiopien 1935-1941, S. 9-27.

because Italy had initially agreed to enter the war only under the contractual requirement that, in the event of victory, the kingdom would receive Trentino, Tyrol, and all of Veneto Giulia, as well as the city of Volosko. The treaty between Italy, France, and Great Britain is the Treaty of London¹¹. However, after the victory, despite this contractual assurance of the Allies, Italy did not receive the agreed territories, but only South Tyrol, Canal Valley, and Trentino. This was much less than the Italian government had demanded Italy's entry into the First World War¹².

In the eyes of the Italians, King Victor Emmanuel II, despite the substantial participation of Italian troops in the victory, had accepted without comment the ignominy of being fobbed off with fewer territories. This unsatisfactory situation was decisive for the king to losing the support of the population vehemently. The resulting ill will against the government grew so immensely that Italy was on the verge of civil war¹³.

The emergence of the imperialist drive

The outcome of the First World War was perceived as a “crippled victory,” and the military development that the Kingdom had undergone provided a national historical explanation for the emergence of a growing imperialist drive in Italy. From a weak army that had suffered a bitter defeat against Abyssinia, the Kingdom of Italy had developed into a militarily consolidated nation that could hold its own in battle. Side by side with the Allies, it had fought and won the First World War.

The Italian people were therefore firmly convinced that their nation had made a decisive contribution to the victory and should rightly be rewarded for it. After all, it was Italian troops who advanced as far as Vittorio-Veneto on October 24, 1918, forcing Austria-Hungary to surrender. The promised lands were not handed over was generally considered an injustice that had to be compensated.

This victory, which was decisive for the outcome of the war, was later incorporated by Mussolini, as a kind of myth, into the ideology of fascism¹⁴. In addition, the defeat at Adua had

¹¹ The Treaty of London dates back to the conference held in London in 1915. The goal of this conference was to have Italy enter the war on the side of the military alliance between Great Britain, France and Russia, called the Triple Entente. The treaty agreed to conclude army and naval agreements against the Central Powers, which would serve to coordinate the war effort. In particular, Russia undertook relief attacks on Austria-Hungary if the latter turned against Italy. France and Great Britain further launched to fight the Austrian fleet in the Mediterranean actively. In return for these assurances, Italy, for its part, undertook to fight all opponents of the alliance with available forces.

¹² The Treaty of London (1915) [http://wwi.lib.byu.edu/index.php/The_Treaty_of_London_\(1915\)](http://wwi.lib.byu.edu/index.php/The_Treaty_of_London_(1915)) (Stand 21.01.2014)

¹³ Giulia Brogini Künzi: Italien und der Abessinienkrieg 1935/36, Paderborn 2002, S. 83-89.

¹⁴ Vgl. Rudolf Lill: Geschichte Italiens vom 16. Jahrhundert bis zu den Anfängen des Faschismus, Darmstadt 1980, S. 287.

not been forgotten by the people, and they longed for retribution for the national prestige, especially against Abyssinia¹⁵. Italy was, therefore, quite receptive to the imperialist aspirations of Fascism and Mussolini's associated war project.

Already during World War I, when Benito Mussolini had served in the Italian military as a bersagliere, he wrote in his diary, later published in German translation as “My war diary” that every fallen Italian was, in fact, a failed Roman¹⁶. By his admission, he was already using the first Roman adaptations at this time. When he was finally appointed prime minister, Mussolini made it his political mission statement to re-establish a Roman empire.

Use of the fasces in party names

At this point, we will briefly discuss the etymology of the Italian word “fascism,” which means “fascism.” The origin of this term goes back to the Latin “fasces,” which in the Roman Republic meant a hatchet tied into a bundle of rods. This ax was carried by so-called lictors as an emblem and served to represent the power of a public official. In German, therefore, the term *Fasces* is often used instead of *Fasces*. Fascism made use of the symbolism of the fasces not only insofar as it was supposed to represent the claim to the power of a public official. The idea of a bundle of rods was also meant to suggest the power of a group of people united in a covenant. Just as a bundle of several rods breaks less quickly than a single rod, an alliance of several people possesses greater power than the individual alone would hold.

However, the use of the term fasces in this way is not a new invention by Benito Mussolini but was already encountered in the 19th century. The *Fasci Siciliani* movement, among others, can be cited as an example of this. Before fascism, the fasces served exclusively as a symbol of the Italian political left, in which Mussolini had participated for several years.

Mussolini was a member of the Italian Socialist Party (PSI) until 1914. He was expelled from the party because, in 1914, he publicly declared that Italy should enter the First World War, even though the rest of the party was against entering the war¹⁷. In 1915, he founded the *Fasci d'Azione Rivoluzionaria*¹⁸ (FAR), another left-wing party, which was dissolved after the First World War.

As can be seen in Mussolini's political beginnings, the use of the fasces, as a constantly recurring element, is already evident here, which he claimed for his goals as early as the naming of the FAR. However, Mussolini only recognized the possibilities offered by the instrumentalization of the Roman past in the political organization *Fasci Italiani di Combattimento*, which

¹⁵ Vgl. Volker Matthies: *Kriege am Horn von Afrika. Historischer Befund und friedenswissenschaftliche Analyse*, Berlin 2005, S. 77-78.

¹⁶ Vgl. Benito Mussolini: *Mein Kriegstagebuch*, Zürich 1930, S. 171.

¹⁷ Vgl. Richard Boswarth: *Mussolini*, New York 2014, S. 90-95.

¹⁸ Vgl. Francesco Leoni: *Storia dei partiti politici italiani*, Napoli 2001, S. 378.

he founded on March 23, 1919¹⁹. Here, for the first time, he flexibly shaped the ideology and decided to define the Roman past as the fixed point “romanità fascista,” allowing him to syncretistically bind together all the elements contained therein²⁰. The founding of the party on November 7, 1921, finally transformed the Fasci Italiani di Combattimento into the Partito Nazionale Fascista (PNF)²¹.

The Fasces as an emblem of fascism

The fasces symbol accompanies fascism in its development like a constant shadow. The PNF carried the fasces in its coat of arms, as did the party's emblem (Fig. 1), and Benito Mussolini's standard also carried the symbol in its flag (Fig. 2). Already between 1921 and 1923, the first party cards containing the fasces can be found (Fig. 3).

During the colonial expansion of fascist Italy, the fasces was also integrated into the flags of the annexed countries. Thus, on the flag of the Italy-Libya colony, which existed from 1934 to 1943, the fasces is fringed by a laurel wreath. (Fig. 4) After the annexation of Abyssinia in 1936, it also adorns the new flag of Italian East Africa (Fig. 5). After the occupation of Albania, two black fascias were added to the Albanian flag in 1939. (Fig. 6).

At the end of World War II, the fasces reappeared in the wartime flag of the Repubblica Sociale Italiana (RSI), founded in 1943 (Fig. 7), which called itself the “Italian Social Republic”. It is noticeable, however, that the flag resembles the “Flag of the Roman Republic 1849” (Fig. 8), which dates from the Risorgimento period²².

Mussolini formulated the motive for the frequent use of the fasces: “The Roman is the lictor's bundle, the Roman is the organization of our fighting associations, the Roman is our pride and our courage”²³. As an ideological aspect, he also mentioned that fascism “demands discipline and authority that penetrates the minds and reigns there unchallenged. Its emblem is, therefore, the lictor bundle, the symbol of unity, strength, and justice”²⁴. With this elevation of the Roman fasces to the ubiquitous emblem, Mussolini achieved that as soon as one speaks of fascism, one always associates this symbol with him until today.

The extent to which the symbolic character described above was pronounced is shown by the fact that after the king deposed Benito Mussolini in 1943, the citizens of Italy destroyed

¹⁹ Vgl. Wolfgang Schieder: *Der Italienische Faschismus*, München 2010, S. 18.

²⁰ Vgl. Emilio Gentile: *Il culto del Littorio. La sacralizzazione della politica nell'Italia fascista*, Rom 1993, S. 212.

²¹ Vgl. Gerhard Feldbauer: *Marsch auf Rom, Faschismus und Antifaschismus in Italien*, Köln 2002, S. 13

²² Vgl. Andrea Giadrina: *Il mito di Roma, da Carlo Magno a Mussolini*, Bari 2008, S. 244-245.

²³ Benito Mussolini: *Opera Omnia*, Bd. XVIII, Florenz 1956, S. 160-161.

²⁴ Vgl. Benito Mussolini: *Der Geist des Faschismus, ein Quellenwerk, herausgegeben und erläutert von Horst Wagenführ*, München 1943, S. 8.

the symbol of the fascias in many places. Particularly noteworthy here is the destruction of the fascias at the “Intituto nazionale per la storia del movimento di liberazione in Italia”²⁵

However, many structures and monuments on which the fascias can be seen still exist today, sometimes because of their functionality. An example is the railroad bridge of the Vatican State Railways, whose construction dates back to the agreement of the Lateran Treaties of 1929. The eight associated arches are decorated alternately with the lictor bundle and the papal coat of arms of Pius XI.

Organization of the March on Rome

In 49 B.C., Julius Caesar forced the fall of the Roman Republic with his march on Rome across the Rubicon. The fascist takeover with the march on Rome in 1922 led to the comparison between Caesar and Mussolini being suggested by historians even during the latter's lifetime.

In 1933, Massimiliano Falciai, among others, argued that this comparison was almost natural, for which he gave the following reasoning: While Caesar's legionaries, with their march on Rome, anticipated the founding of the Roman Empire, the Fascist march on Rome was intended to put an end to the situation in the Kingdom of Italy, which had become intolerable, and to save the nation from disintegration by consolidating the unity achieved by the Fatherland²⁶.

With a star-shaped deployment of fascist militia, the March on Rome was to herald the era of fascism emphatically. While the troops were taking a position outside the city, King Victor Emmanuel III finally appointed Benito Mussolini as Prime Minister of Italy. During the march on Rome, Mussolini threatened to occupy the parliament building if his demands were unmet. He did not use the Italian term “squadristi” for the occupation unit but deliberately gave it the Roman designation “manipoli”²⁷. In the following, the military organization of the march on Rome will be examined in more detail. The fascist militia that invaded Rome was organized by Mussolini strictly according to the principle of the Roman military hierarchy. The individual divisions bore the following names: “manipoli”, “centurie”, “coorti” and “legioni”, which in turn were subordinate to the “decurioni”, “centurioni”, “seniori” and “consoli”. The four military commanders at the top were given the title “quadrumviri”, an ancient Roman designation probably chosen about the triumvirates of Caesar and Augustus.

Ancient Roman rituals were also used to recognize the fascist militia. Mussolini, for example, used a variation of the Roman salute, called “Salute Romano” in Italian to enforce

²⁵ Vgl. Andrea Giadrina: *Il mito di Roma*, Bari 2008, S. 244-245.

²⁶ Vgl. Frank Vollmer, *Die politische Kultur des Faschismus. Stätten totalitär Diktatur in Italien*, Köln 2007. S.327.

²⁷ Vgl. Ebd., S. 17.

military discipline²⁸. In addition to the Roman salute, he introduced the so-called Roman marching step for the military, known in Italian as the “*Marcia fascista*”²⁹. This bore a strong resemblance to the Prussian marching step. Still, Mussolini summarily rejected this, claiming that the Prussian marching step was, in turn, merely an imitation of the Roman marching step³⁰.

It can be seen that Mussolini used Roman adaptations in the organization of his troops to be able to present the March on Rome as an ideological self-presentation. In this sense, the March on Rome was meant to herald a resumption of the imperial years of rule. Beginning in 1926, the fascists' seizure of power was officially declared an “*era fascista*”³¹. The significance of the political overthrow by the fascists was also underlined by the introduction of fascist commemorative days, the so-called “*giornate fasciste*”. These were the founding day of the city of Rome on April 21 (753 B.C.), the founding of the *Fasci Italiani di Combattimento* on March 23 (1919), and the March on Rome on October 28 (1922).

Mussolini's self-dramatization as the second Augustus

Fascism confiscated three jubilees from the Augustan period in honor of Roman antiquity. The first jubilee was celebrated in 1930 in honor of the birth of Virgil³². The second jubilee followed in 1935 in honor of the birth of Horace³³. A third jubilee followed in 1937 in honor of the birth of Emperor Augustus³⁴.

To emphasize the importance of the Roman emperor Augustus for fascism, Mussolini had a unique stamp printed for his 2000th birthday. Celebrating a jubilee in honor of Augustus came up as early as 1930. Moreover, in 1932 it was decided to organize an exhibition under the title “*Mostra Augustea della Romanità*” (Augustan Exhibition of Romanism) from September 23, 1937, to November 6, 1938³⁵.

This exhibition was intended to equate Mussolini's and Augustus' claims to power. In a lecture on “*The Italy of Augustus and the Italy of Today*,” Fascist cultural politician Giuseppe Bottai portrayed the Roman emperor Augustus as a kind of precursor to Mussolini. In support

²⁸ Vgl. Wolfgang Schieder: Rom – die Repräsentation der Antike im Faschismus in: Elke Stein Hölkeskamp u. Karl-Joachim Hölkeskamp (Hg.), *Erinnerungs Orte der Antike. Die Römische Welt*, München 2006, S. 701-723. Hier S. 703.

²⁹ Vgl. Simonetta Falasca Zamponi: *Lo spettacolo del fascismo*, Soveria Mannelli 2003, S. 11.

³⁰ Vgl. Benito Mussolini: *Opera Omnia*, Bd. XVI, Florenz 1955, S. 244.

³¹ Vgl. Emilio Gentile: *Il culto del Littorio*, Rom 1993, S. 100-105.

³² Vergil (Publius Vergilius Maro) wurde 70 v. Chr. in Mantua geboren.

³³ Horaz (Quintus Horatius Flaccus) wurde 65 v. Chr. in Venusia (dem heutigen Venosa) geboren.

³⁴ Kaiser Augustus (Octavian) wurde 63 v. Chr. in Rom geboren. Im Jahre 27 v. Chr. verlieh der Senat Octavian den Ehrennamen Augustus; Das Jahr 27 v. Chr. markiert zudem den Beginn seines Prinzipats.

³⁵ Vgl. Friedemann Scriba, *Augustus im Schwarzhemd? Die mostra Augustea della Romanità in Rom 1937/38*, Frankfurt am Main 1995, S. 26-27.

of this thesis, Bottai argued that both brought about a legal revolution and brought internal peace to their empires through their rule³⁶.

In 1921, Benito Mussolini gave himself the Latin title “DUX”, in Italian pronunciation “Duce”, about Octavian's title “August”. This title had no constitutional status, but like the title “Augustus,” it had a timeless, Roman appeal. The perception that this title evoked among the Italian people was described by Curzio Malaparte as follows: “He is no longer Mussolini: he is already the firstborn son of the Roman she-wolf, he is already the Duce, he is already the new Caesar, the new Augustus, he is already the Heros, predestined to become God³⁷.”

Looking at the biographies written during Mussolini's lifetime, it is clear that already in the 1920s and 1930s, he was portrayed by some authors as the reincarnation of a faithful Roman. One example is the 1932 biography of Mussolini by Kurt Kornicker³⁸, in which he conveys the image that Mussolini was sacrificing himself for Italy and striving for a rebirth of antiquity like a faithful Roman. Another example is the 1927 biography of Mussolini written by Margherita Sarfatti. In it, Mussolini's mistress described him as follows: “Benito Mussolini is a Roman, both in soul and countenance; he is the reunion of the pure Italian type, which for centuries has come to a new flowering³⁹“. In addition to numerous writings aimed primarily at an adult audience, measures were also taken to introduce the ideology of fascism to children, young people, and the illiterate. Comics, in particular, were an essential medium for imprinting young people. One example is the comic strip “Andus e I Lupi del Nord” (Fig. 9), intended to show even the youngest generation that Italy was in a phase of revival and continuation of the Roman heritage and depicted Mussolini together with Emperor August. In addition, the comic as a medium was also aimed at the part of the Italian population that could not read and write. This factor should not be underestimated since, at the time of fascism, 49.9% of the Italian population was still illiterate⁴⁰.

Conclusion

As our investigation reveals, the motive of restoration of Roman antiquity already existed during the formation of the nation-state in Italy. During the Risorgimento, however, it was impossible to do justice to Rome's re-emergence in the sense of an ideology of

³⁶ Giuseppe Bottai: *L'Italia di Augusto e l'Italia di oggi*, Rom 1937.

³⁷ Curzio Malaparte: *Mussolini il grande imbecile*, Mailand 1999, S. 53.

³⁸ Vgl. Kurt Kornicker: *Mussolini aus der Nähe*, Lübeck 1932, S. 24-25.

³⁹ Margherita Sarfatti: *Mussolini, Lebensgeschichte nach autobiographischen Unterlagen*, Leipzig 1927, S. 2.

⁴⁰ Vgl. Raseri: *La popolazione israelitica in Italia*, *Atti della società romana di antropologia*, Rom 1904, S. 88

integration. With the defeat at the Battle of Adua, Italy's colonial aspirations were discarded for the time being at this point.

Under Mussolini, new life was breathed into the ideology of a restoration of the Roman Empire, elevating it to the all-pervasive foundation and political guiding principle of the Fascist movement. Both the Risorgimento and Fascism appealed to a renaissance of Roman antiquity for Italy. But only fascism succeeded in establishing this goal as a long-term ideological basis.

From the March on Rome in 1922 to the proclamation of the Empire in 1936, the pursuit of Rome's former greatness represented the central leitmotif for the mentality of Fascist Italy. Through his adaptations of Romanism, Mussolini could portray himself as the legitimate successor to Augustus since he was free to decide what was “Roman” and what was not. The underlying goals of an expansionist policy were highly ideologically charged, and the masses were deliberately moved to support fascism by celebrating Italian Romanism.

After the proclamation of the Italian Empire, the euphoria for the ancient Roman culture slowly died out, as did the interest in a revival of the Roman Empire. After World War II, the glorification of Roman antiquity ebbed rapidly, as it was of little political interest or note to Fascism. By 1943 at the latest, after Mussolini was deposed, Roman imperial ideology was finally discarded and no longer played a central role for Italy. This shows that the fascist ideology of restoration of ancient Rome, despite widely propagated claims, served primarily as a tool to legitimize fascism's claim to power in Italy and to make Mussolini's imperial expansionist policy palatable to the people.

With the proclamation of the Italian Empire, Mussolini saw the way paved for an adaptation of the Imperium Romanum. However, Mussolini's plans to restore the Italian nation to the former power of Rome under his political leadership soon failed during the Second World War. With the entry into the war in 1940, the “romanità fascista” was no longer significant since more urgent problems had to be addressed. The national enthusiasm for acting as Rome's heir was entirely extinguished by the fall of Mussolini on July 25, 1943.

The question of whether Fascist Italy now constituted an empire simply because it was proclaimed as such, as well as the question of whether Mussolini was ultimately a second Augustus simply because he allowed himself to be celebrated as such, can be answered by the devastating developments during the impending outcome of World War II. After his deposition by the fascist Grand Council, Mussolini led the Social Republic of Italy, finally only a puppet government under Germany. In an attempt to escape to Switzerland, he was ultimately shot by Italian partisans.

Whether fascist Italy was an empire is to be denied. Just because Mussolini solemnly proclaimed Italy an “Imperio”, and the people received this message with jubilation, it is not necessarily to be recognized historically.

Illustrations:

(Fig. 1.: Stemma Partito Nazionale Fascista)

(Fig. 2.: Personal flag of Benito Mussolini)

(Fig. 3.: Tessera del partito, Party card)

(Fig. 4.: Lo stemma coloniale della Libia, Coat of arms of the colony of Italian Libya)

(Fig. 5.: Flag of the Viceroy of Italian East Africa)

(Fig. 6.: National flag of the Kingdom of Albania 1939-1943)

(Fig. 7.: War flag of the Italian Social Republic)

(Fig. 8.: Flag of the Roman Republic 1849)

(Fig. 9.: Comic: Il fascismo a fumetti, Augustus and the Duce)